

BC-SIM-TN-015

simAir User Manual

Version 1

Sergio Fonte¹, Michele Zusi¹, Emanuele Simioni², Romolo Politi¹,
Gabriele Cremonese², Fabrizio Capaccioni¹, Alain Doressoundiram³,
Pasquale Palumbo¹, Cristina Re², Mathieu Vincendon⁴

¹IINAF-IAPS Via Fosso del Cavaliere 100, 00133, Rome, Italy

²IINAF-OAPD Vicolo Osservatorio 5,35122, Padua, Italy

³Observatoire de Paris, Laboratoire d'Études Spatiales et d'Instrumentation en Astrophysique (LESIA),
92195 Meudon Cedex, France

⁴Institut d'Astrophysique Spatiale, CNRS / Université Paris Sud, 91405, Orsay, France

Document BC-SIM-TN-015
Date 03/10/23
Issue 1
Revision 0
Page 2 of 12

Index

INDEX.....	2
APPROVATION	3
DOCUMENT CHANGE RECORD.....	3
1 INTRODUCTION.....	4
1.1 SCOPE	4
1.2 REFERENCE DOCUMENT	4
1.3 ACRONYMS	4
1.4 DOCUMENT FORMAT AND REPOSITORY.....	5
2 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION	6
3 INPUT AND OUTPUT.....	8
3.1 INPUT.....	8
3.2 OUTPUT.....	9
3.3 NOTES.....	11
4 VERSION	12
5 VERSION HISTORY	12

Document BC-SIM-TN-015
Date 03/10/23
Issue 1
Revision 0
Page 3 of 12

Approval

Edited by:	
	Sergio Fonte
	Michele Zusi
	Emanuele Simioni
	Romolo Politi
Approved by:	
	Gabriele Cremonese
	Fabrizio Capaccioni
	Alain Doressoundiram
	Pasquale Palumbo
	Cristina Re
	Mathieu Vincendon

Document Change Record

Issue	Revision	Date	Affected Pages	Change description
1	0	03/10/2023	All	First issue

Document BC-SIM-TN-015
Date 03/10/23
Issue 1
Revision 0
Page 4 of 12

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document describes the software simAir, used to convert the HouseKeeping (HK) and science TeLeMetries (TLM) into raw data for the MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory – SYStem (SIMBIO-SYS) instrument suite onboard the ESA mission BepiColombo to Mercury.

The input for simAir is an XML file containing a sequence of packets in SCOS-2000 format; the description of each telemetry packet is extracted and stored into different folders and files that will be described in the following sections. The housekeeping are converted from Digital Number (DN) to physical unit using a SQLite database.

1.2 Reference Document

- [RD.1] BC-SIM-TN-003 – Reports and Notes Layout and Flow – Version 2, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179)
- [RD.2] BC-SIM-GAF-IC-002 – SIMBYO-SYS Software Interface Control Document – rev. 14
- [RD.3] EGOS-MCS-S2K-ICD-0001 - SCOS-2000 Database Import ICD – Issue 7.0 - FINAL

1.3 Acronyms

DN	Digital Number
HK	HouseKeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
NAIF	Navigation and Ancillary Information Facility
PDS4	Planetary Data System version 4
SCOS-2000	Satellite Control and Operation System 2000
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SPICE	Spacecraft ephemeris, Planet, Instrument information, C-orientation, Events
LSK	LeapSeconds Kernel
SCLK	Spacecraft Clock Kernel
UTC	Universal Time Coordinated
ET	Ephemeris Time
STC	STereo imaging Channel
TLM	TeLeMetry
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
XML	eXtensible Markup Language
VIHI	Visible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel

Document	BC-SIM-TN-015
Date	03/10/23
Issue	1
Revision	0
Page	5 of 12

1.4 Document Format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD.1] and will be archived both on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

Document BC-SIM-TN-015
Date 03/10/23
Issue 1
Revision 0
Page 6 of 12

2 Software description

simAir is a program written in C/C++ language in order to have the best time performance into the processing of the SCOS-2000 telemetries. It elaborates each single packet of the SIMBIO-SYS TLM file and interprets the binary information as described in [RD.2].

Figure 1 reports a general scheme of the structure where *simAir* performs its activities, in particular *simAir* use the following folders and files:

- the *input* folder contains the SCOS-2000 file (in xml format) to be elaborate
- the *confisData* folder contains:
 - *simAirConversionTable_v05.db* which is an SQLite database used to store the parameters used to convert the HK values from digital numbers into physical values.
- the output folder contains the output products describe in paragraph 3.2.
- the *kernels* folder contains the SPICE-NAIF kernels, the structure of the folder respects the guide lines of NAIF (see the link <https://naif.jpl.nasa.gov/naif/index.html> as reference); in particular for *simAir* there are only two type of kernels that are used and are stored in the folders:
 - in LSK folder there is *naif0012.tls* file used in conversions between ET and UTC.
 - In SCLK folder there is *bc_mpo_step_20210408.tsc* file used in conversions between SCLK and ET.
- the *simbio.mk* is the SPICE meta-kernel file use by *simAir* to convert the spacecraft time into UTC time, this file contains the absolute paths pointing to the kernels of the kernels folder.

Figure 1: *simAir* operating structure.

The *simAir* simplest execution command is, see Table 1 for details of the options:

```

simAir -f input/bc-sim-tm2raw-20181210T000000-20181211T000000-20190604T210348_joined_cl.xml
-x -c configData/config.xml -m simbio.mk -d configData/simAirConversionTable_v05.db -o
output
  
```

In the following sections, the above string together with all its parameters are described.

3 Input and output

3.1 Input

Table 1 lists all the simAir call options and an example of its usage.

Option name	Shortcut	Description and example
--help	-h	Print help and quit from the script
--apid	-a	Set the APID to process (this parameter is not active now) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> APID_VIHI = 100 <input type="checkbox"/> APID_STC = 101 <input type="checkbox"/> APID_HRIC = 103 Example: --apid 103
--log_level	-l	Set the level of logging; the conventional meaning of the log_level is defined as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 : action must be taken immediately <input type="checkbox"/> 2 : critical conditions <input type="checkbox"/> 3 : error conditions <input type="checkbox"/> 4 : warning conditions <input type="checkbox"/> 5 : normal but significant condition <input type="checkbox"/> 6 : informational <input type="checkbox"/> 7 : debug-level messages the default value is 3. Example: --log_level 3
--filename	-f	Set the file to process Example: -filename input/bc-sim-tm2raw-20181210T000000-20181211T000000-20190604T210348_joined_cl.xml
--is_xml	-x	A boolean value to indicated the input file is in SCOS-2000 xml format (otherwise the program does nothing) Example: --is_xml
--conf	-c	Set the config file for simAir Example: --conf configData/config.xml
--metakernel	-m	Set the meta-kernel file that contains the SPICE-NAIF kernels for time conversion

		Example: --metakernel simbio.mk
--output_folder	-o	Set the folder where the simAir file will be generated; here will be created also the file <i>simAir.log</i> that contains the log of the program Example: --output_folder output
--database	-d	Set the file database useful to convert the digital numbers into physical quantities for those housekeeping fields that need this transformation. Example: --database configData/simAirConversionTable_v05.db
--version	-v	Get version of the program in standard output and quit from the program Example: --version

Table 1: List of simAir program options.

3.2 Output

The output folder is composed as follows:

- two log files:
 - *packets.log*: it reports the packet header in csv format of the SCOSS-2000 file provided in input to simAir
 - *simAir.log*: it consists into the log of the program execution
- n folders with the following name convention:

<SCET>_<COARSE_TIME>_<FINE_TIME>_<PID>_<PCAT>_<counter_detector>, see the [RD.2] for the meaning of each field; <counter_detector> is a progressive number that starts from 0 to the number of frames for each detector. These folders contain:

 - Private Science TML Header (see [RD.2]) is a csv file with the following columns:
 - Subframe filename
 - SourceSequenceCount
 - PacketLength
 - NbBoundary
 - CompressionBox
 - RkWindows
 - RkSubFrameRow
 - RkSubFrameCol
 - IBR
 - Flag

The header of *private_science_tm_header.csv* file contains the previous list of fields, for the meaning of the fields see [RD.2].

- m binary files (subframe) with the data from the detector in compressed mode, with the extension “.bin”. The name of subframe file follows this convention:
subframe_<RKWINDOW>_<XSIZE>_<YSIZE>_<IBR>_<COMPRESSOR_BOX>_<RKSUBFRAME_COL>_<RKSUBFRAME_ROW>.bin
 see the [RD.2] for the meaning of each field.
- A csv file with the HK fields in physical units of the detector. The name of the file follows this convention:
sim_hk_<CHANNEL>_xxx_<NWIN>_<FILTERS>_NNNNN_<ACQ_TIME>.csv
 where:
 - <CHANNEL> = hric_low | hric_high | stc_low | stc_high | vihi_low | vihi_high
 - <NWIN> = number of windows for STC and HRIC
 - <FILTERS> = filters of STC and HRIC
 - For VIHI <NWIN>_<FILTERS> are substituted with spectrometer mode.
 - <ACQ_TIME> = is the acquisition time.

The parameters necessary to decompress the data from the detector, is stored in the file with extension “.win”; in this file the values of the fields reported in the Table 2 are stored.

Files name	Description	Detector
NSS2002	Integration time	STC, HRIC, VIHI
NSS3007	Rk frame	STC, HRIC, VIHI
NSS32010	Start Pixel row coordinate	VIHI
NSS32011	Start Pixel column coordinate	VIHI
NSS32012	End Pixel row coordinate	VIHI
NSS32013	End Pixel column coordinate	VIHI
NSSD3310	Spatial Binning	VIHI
NSSD3311	Binning on frameSequence	VIHI
NSSD3312	Spectral editing	VIHI
NSSD3313	Binning/Editing	VIHI
NSSD210	Number Windows	STC, HRIC
NSSD211	Binning W2	HRIC
NSSD212	Binning W1	HRIC
NSSD213	Binning W6	HRIC
NSSD214	Binning W5	HRIC
NSSD215	Binning W4	HRIC
NSSD216	Binning W3	HRIC
NSSD220	W1 Start Pixel-row	STC, HRIC
NSSD221	W1 Start Pixel-col	STC, HRIC
NSSD222	W1 End Pixel-row	STC, HRIC
NSSD223	W1 End Pixel-col	STC, HRIC

Document BC-SIM-TN-015
Date 03/10/23
Issue 1
Revision 0
Page 12 of 12

4 Version

The current version of the software is 2.1.1.

5 Version History

- 1.0.0 Original version
- 2.1.0 Update Acquisition time to PSA format (for all channels and ME) into HK csv files
- 2.1.1 Update Acquisition time to PSA format (for all channels and ME) into HK csv files: increase number of digit for coarse time from 9 to 10 digits.